

Conductance Studies of Triphenylphosphoniumoxo-halouranates (VI) and the Electronic Spectra of some Dixouranium (VI) Complexes

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The complexes, $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2[\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_4]$ and $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2[\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_4]$ show interesting behaviour in acetonitrile and methanol solvents as borne out by the $\sqrt{C_M}$ vs Λ_M plot of the complexes. The electronic spectra of these two complexes as also of a number of other complexes isolated having the general formulae $\text{UO}_2\text{X}_2\text{L}_2$ or 3 and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{Ph}_2\text{SO})_5](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ [$\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_3, \text{NCS}$ and $\text{L} = \text{Quinoline N-oxide}, \text{Ph}_2\text{SO}$ and $(\text{PhO})_3\text{PO}$] have been recorded in suitable solvents. From the detailed Gaussian analyses of the spectra it is evident that the transitions within uranyl (VI) group are dependent on the secondary ligands (other than the oxygen atoms of the oxocation); the so called 'uranyl (VI) region' of the spectra is characterized by several vibrational fine structures.

THE preparations and characterization of a large number of dioxouranium (VI) and uranium (IV) complexes with both anionic (chloro and bromo) as also neutral unidentate oxygen donor ligands having $\text{X} = \text{O}$ grouping [$\text{X} = \text{N}$, (quinoline N-oxide), P (triphenyl phosphine oxide, triphenyl phosphate and hexamethyl phosphoramide) or S (diphenyl sulphoxide)] have been reported from this laboratory with a detailed discussion of the infrared spectra¹⁻⁴ and magnetic properties⁵ of these complexes. Owing to the fact that the neutral complexes give conducting solutions in methanol and also because of the interesting behaviour of the oxohalouranates (VI) during fractional crystallisation in acetonitrile it has now been considered worthwhile to make a detailed study of their conductance concentration data in different solvents in an attempt to rationalize the above behaviours and also to explain the infrared data related to the nonlinearity of the UO_2^{2+} ion. Moreover, contrary to the observations of McGlynn *et al.*⁶ the present authors find that the T $\leftarrow$ S transition in the 'uranyl (VI) spectra' is not insensitive to equatorial ligation and so the details of the spectral data of the isolated dioxouranium (VI) complexes are also incorporated.

Discussion

The complexes $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_4$ and $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_4$ are soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, dioxane, tetrahydrofuran and also moderately soluble in acetonitrile and nitromethane, but are insoluble in benzene, chloroform, ether, light petroleum and carbon tetrachloride. From the alcoholic solutions the substances cannot be crystallised, because in these solvents (methanol and ethanol) they undergo irreversible dissociation. From the acetonitrile solution the crystallisation of the complexes is slow and when generally two crops of the crystals of $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{UO}_2\text{X}_4$

are taken out, the dilute solution on further concentration deposits the corresponding triphenyl phosphonium halide leaving a yellow mother liquor obviously containing appropriate uranium (VI) salt. To understand this behaviour a thorough study of the molar conductance of $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_4$ and $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_4$ in acetonitrile solution is undertaken and the conductance-concentration data are presented in the Table 1 and the corresponding Λ_M vs $\sqrt{C_M}$ plots are shown in Fig. 1. The data in Table 1 indicate that at relatively higher concentration the Λ_M values are markedly lower than what is expected for 2 : 1 electrolytes in this solvent⁷. This may presumably be due to the association through hydrogen bonding between the hydrogen atoms attached to the phosphorus in triphenyl phosphonium cations and the oxygen atoms of the UO_2^{2+} ion present in the anion. It may be recalled here that this association phenomenon accounts for (i) the lowering of the P-H stretch⁸ in the infrared spectra of the compounds like $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{UO}_2\text{X}_4$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br) than that of the complex $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_6$ and (ii) the loss of $D_{\infty h}$ symmetry of the UO_2^{2+} ion, as U-O...H configuration will be angular, and the appearance of an anomalous symmetric stretch⁹ of the said ion in the infrared spectra. It is also noticed (Table 1) that with dilution the conductivities increase sharply until a maximum value is reached and then drop to lower values. This behaviour (c.f. Fig. 1) tempts us to suggest a two stage equilibria depending on dilution, as

TABLE I—MOLAR CONDUCTANCE—CONCENTRATION DATA OF THE OXOHALO URANATES (VI) IN CH₃CN AT 30°

Compound	Molar concentrations ($\sqrt{C_M} \times 10^2$)						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
$\Lambda_M(\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2)$ (Ph ₃ PH) ₂ UO ₂ Cl ₄	7.87 93	4.58 105	4.00 130	3.32 156	2.70 163	1.57 143	1.11 107
$\Lambda_M(\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2)$ (Ph ₃ PH) ₂ UO ₂ Br ₄	7.50 132	6.16 137	4.00 152	2.90 170	1.00 143	0.87 129	— —

(where X = Cl or Br)

The hydrogen halide molecules may be associated with triphenyl phosphine lowering the conductance values and helping towards the deposition of Ph₃PHX leaving behind UO₂X₂ which has been shown⁹ to behave as an appreciably weak electrolyte in acetonitrile solution at even a very low concentration. Even if it is assumed that the association of HX with Ph₃P is very weak in solution, the free HX (most particularly the HCl) is known as a weak electrolyte

Fig. 1. $\sqrt{C_M}$ vs Λ_M plots of (A) (Ph₃PH)₂UO₂Cl₄ and (B) (Ph₃PH)₂UO₂Br₄ in acetonitrile.

in acetonitrile, with appreciably low molar conductance values, even at low acid concentration when the ions of the type CH₃CNH⁺ and X⁻ predominate. All these favour the formulation of the above two stage equilibria. The molecular rearrangement at higher dilution is expected to lower the conductance values sufficiently but since the concentration of the intermediate 2 : 1 electrolytic species is still quite appreciable at even very high dilution, the drastic fall of the conductance values is inhibited

Visible and ultraviolet spectra :

The electronic spectra of these complexes furnish the following three types of absorption due to :

- (a) transitions within the UO₂²⁺ ion,
- (b) secondary ligands → UO₂²⁺ charge transfer, and
- (c) transitions within the organic ligand molecule.

The salient observations and their interpretations are outlined as follows :

(a) The uranyl spectrum in the visible region (400–500 nm) is due to the coupling of several vibrational frequencies of the complex, principally the

symmetrical O–U–O frequencies¹¹, to several fairly closely spaced very weak or forbidden (T ← S) electron transfer transition^{6, 12}. The spin selection rule of this electronic transition has been broken down due to spin orbit coupling. Transition having oscillator strengths upto ~ 10⁴ have been observed in quinoline N-oxide complexes (Table 2) in diphenyl sulphoxide complexes (Table 3) in triphenyl phosphate complex (Table 4) and in the oxohalo complexes (Table 5). From the data and from the profiles of the spectra (Figs. 2–7), as worked out by Gaussian analysis, it appears that the principal effect of ligand environment on the uranyl spectrum is on the relative intensities, the numbers and also on the energies of the series of peaks. Since the bands are not at all independent of equatorial ligation, the assignment of correct symmetry species of the excited triplet state of the UO₂²⁺ ion⁶ and hence the location of the bands (as made by McGlynn *et al.*⁹) corresponding to the different triplet multiplets are extremely difficult. So, no attempts has been made to find out the mean vibrational intervals.

In the case of the quinoline N-oxide thiocyanate complex, UO₂(NCS)₂3QO, the low energy tail of the charge transfer band, SCN → UO₂²⁺, completely masks the transitions due to UO₂²⁺ group (Fig. 3B). The profiles of the spectra of the bromo complexes, UO₂Br₂2QO, UO₂Br₂3Ph₂SO and (Ph₃PH)₂UO₂Br₄ (Figs. 2B, 4B and 7B respectively) also show that the low energy tail of the Br → UO₂²⁺ charge transfer

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA OF THE QUINOLINE N-OXIDE COMPLEXES IN METHANOL

Compound	$\bar{\nu}_{max}$ (cm ⁻¹)	Oscillator strength f^*
UO ₂ Cl ₂ 2QO	20,160	9.63 × 10 ⁻⁶
	20,830	3.45 × 10 ⁻⁵
	21,790	1.07 × 10 ⁻⁴
	22,730	1.18 × 10 ⁻⁴
	23,580	1.99 × 10 ⁻⁴
UO ₂ Br ₂ 2QO	20,830	4.09 × 10 ⁻⁵
	21,320	7.11 × 10 ⁻⁶
	21,650	5.33 × 10 ⁻⁵
	22,220	4.77 × 10 ⁻⁵
	22,730	6.86 × 10 ⁻⁵
	23,200	4.01 × 10 ⁻⁵
UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ 2QO	23,810	1.33 × 10 ⁻⁵
	20,410	1.88 × 10 ⁻⁵
	21,280	1.09 × 10 ⁻⁴
	22,220	1.09 × 10 ⁻⁴
UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ 2QO	22,990	2.32 × 10 ⁻⁴
	23,980	3.10 × 10 ⁻⁴
	Obscured	

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE DIPHENYL SULPHOXIDE COMPLEXES IN DICHLOROMETHANE

Compound	$\bar{\nu}_{max}$ (cm ⁻¹)	Oscillator strength f^*
UO ₂ Cl ₂ ·2Ph ₂ SO	20,000	1.51 × 10 ⁻⁵
	20,830	2.76 × 10 ⁻⁵
	22,030	4.65 × 10 ⁻⁵
	23,090	4.78 × 10 ⁻⁵
	23,810	4.77 × 10 ⁻⁵
UO ₂ Br ₂ ·3Ph ₂ SO	20,160	1.10 × 10 ⁻⁶
	20,580	1.54 × 10 ⁻⁵
	21,320	2.90 × 10 ⁻⁵
	22,030	6.72 × 10 ⁻⁵
	22,830	2.51 × 10 ⁻⁵
UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·2Ph ₂ SO	20,830	1.95 × 10 ⁻⁶
	21,280	1.06 × 10 ⁻⁵
	21,930	1.41 × 10 ⁻⁵
	22,730	6.11 × 10 ⁻⁵
	23,580	7.64 × 10 ⁻⁵
	24,210	9.66 × 10 ⁻⁵
[UO ₂ (Ph ₂ SO) ₅](ClO ₄) ₂	20,830	1.67 × 10 ⁻⁵
	21,740	4.08 × 10 ⁻⁵
	22,470	9.09 × 10 ⁻⁵
	23,260	9.19 × 10 ⁻⁵
	24,100	1.11 × 10 ⁻⁵

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF UO₂(NO₃)₂·2(PhO)₂ PO IN CH₂Cl₂

Band position (cm ⁻¹)	Oscillator strength f^*
20,410	3.45 × 10 ⁻⁶
21,280	1.43 × 10 ⁻⁵
22,220	1.84 × 10 ⁻⁵
22,830	2.18 × 10 ⁻⁵
23,310	3.01 × 10 ⁻⁵
23,980	5.37 × 10 ⁻⁵
24,630	1.71 × 10 ⁻⁵
25,130	1.78 × 10 ⁻⁵
25,910	1.42 × 10 ⁻⁵

TABLE 5—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF OXOHALO URANATES (VI) IN ACETONITRILE

Compound	$\bar{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹)	Oscillator strength f^*	
(Ph ₃ PH) ₂ UO ₂ Cl ₄	19,880	5.52 × 10 ⁻⁷	
	20,240	8.00 × 10 ⁻⁶	
	20,580	2.30 × 10 ⁻⁶	
	21,010	1.07 × 10 ⁻⁵	
	21,740	9.87 × 10 ⁻⁶	
	22,520	3.09 × 10 ⁻⁵	
	23,260	4.71 × 10 ⁻⁵	
	24,330	2.77 × 10 ⁻⁵	
	(Ph ₃ PH) ₂ UO ₂ Br ₄	19,800	7.36 × 10 ⁻⁷
		20,080	1.24 × 10 ⁻⁵
20,790		1.52 × 10 ⁻⁵	
21,550		2.05 × 10 ⁻⁵	
22,220		2.70 × 10 ⁻⁵	
22,880		2.40 × 10 ⁻⁵	

* Defined by $f = 4.60 \times 10^{-9} \epsilon_{max} \sigma$, where σ is the width of the band (in cm⁻¹) measured at half height¹³.

band also enters within the visible uranyl region and bands due to UO₂²⁺ group are found to "borrow" intensity from the said charge transfer bands. By detailed Gaussian analysis, however, it has been possible to get qualitatively the true intensities of the UO₂²⁺ bands in those complexes, but the bands in high energy region which are observed in other complexes are masked in the bromo complexes by the said low energy tail. The Br⁻ and NCS⁻ being quite reducible ligands the charge transfer bands mentioned are naturally within the visible region. The spectral data recorded in the Tables 2-5 for the chloro, nitrate and perchlorate compounds, only show probably two components of T ← S bands, the other such component and the transitions S* ← S, the perturbing singlets⁶, are all hidden within the very intense ultraviolet bands due to charge transfer (ligand → UO₂²⁺) and the transitions within the organic ligand molecule.

(b) Since the quinoline N-oxide complexes are only soluble in highly interacting methanol solvent, the exact position of the ligand → UO₂²⁺ charge transfer bands in the N-oxide complexes could not be located because to record a reasonably correct spectrum in the ultra-violet region, a very low concentration of the complex in the solvent is required. At such a high dilution in methanol, the latter has the chance to solvate the complex species as discussed elsewhere⁹ and thereby to remove the anionic ligands from the coordination sphere to a significant extent. Other charge transfer bands (QO → UO₂²⁺) are probably obscured within the π → π* transition of the quinoline N-oxide molecule.

From the solutions obtained by shaking the UO₂Br₂·3Ph₂SO and [UO₂(Ph₂SO)₅](ClO₄)₂ separately with cyclohexane for twenty four hours, the former shows a broad absorption maxima spreading through the region 288 (34,720) to 312 nm (32,050 cm⁻¹) probably due to Br → UO₂²⁺ charge transfer occluded with other charge transfer bands. This type of band observed in the perchlorate compound, centred at 290 nm (34,480 cm⁻¹) is less broad.

(c) Quinoline N-oxide dihydrate in methanol solution has shown a π → π* transition at 340 nm i.e., 29,410 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon_{max} = 9680$) characteristic of the N-oxide group. Again in methanol solution, the quinoline N-oxide complexes show a hypsochromic shift of the band at 324 nm (30,860 cm⁻¹) irrespective of the anionic ligands. This observation supports the solvation phenomena of the complexes⁹ in this solvent at high dilution.

In cyclohexane solvent, diphenyl sulphoxide is found to give two absorption bands at 234 nm (42,740 cm⁻¹) and 268 nm (37,310 cm⁻¹), with log ϵ values of 4.10 and 3.25, respectively. These two are identified¹⁴ as strongly perturbed $1La$ and $1Lb$ (Platt notations¹⁵) transitions, respectively. The lack of a clean separation of the two bands (the higher wavelength band being only an inflection) has been presumed¹⁴ to be due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition which occurs between $1La$ and $1Lb$. However, because the $1La$ band undergoes a bathochromic shift of 5 nm on changing the solvent from cyclohexane to ethanol

Fig. 2. The electronic spectra and their Gaussian analyses in methanol.

(A) $\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$
 (B) $\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ } Cell thickness 2 cm.

Fig. 3 The electronic spectra and their Gaussian analyses in methanol.

(A) $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$
 (B) $\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot 3\text{QO}$

this band (234 nm; $42,740 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is suggested¹⁵ to be the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band characteristic of the sulphoxide. In all the complexes the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band is hypsochromically shifted, indicating coordination through the oxygen atom of the sulphoxide. This blue shift is more marked in the bromo complex where the band is located at 226 ($44,250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), than in the perchlorate compound, where the same is found at 230 nm ($43,480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and in the remaining two complexes, viz., the chloro and the nitrate complexes, the band is located at 232 nm ($43,100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) presumably the strength of the sulphoxide coordination is reduced in the above order. In the complexes, the separation between $1L_a$ and $1L_b$ bands are more distinct which obviously is due to the disappearance

of $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ band of the free sulphoxide after complex formation.

Experimental

Solvent purifications :

The G.R. (E. Merck) quality methanol, cyclohexane and dichloromethane were distilled before use. Acetonitrile (extra pure Riedel) was treated with P_2O_5 , kept for 2 days and then distilled and the process was repeated until further addition of P_2O_5 did not impart any yellow colouration to the latter. The middle fractions of the solvents so purified were used for absorption and conductance measurements.

Conductance measurements :

Mullard conductivity bridge type E 7566/2 was used for the measurement of conductance in a large stoppered cell with cell constant of 0.13. These measured values were randomly checked by Phillips G.M. 4249.

The purified solvents and the solutions of the complex species were always kept in desiccators over fused calcium chloride and every possible precaution was taken to prevent moisture contamination during use. All measurements were made at 30° in a well-regulated thermostat with the help of a thermometer capable of recording a change of 0.1° .

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectra were studied in Nujol mulls and recorded on Perkin-Elmer's 'Infracord' equipped with rock salt optics. The chart papers were calibrated with recommended polystyrene bands.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra were measured in Hilger U.V. spectrophotometer in the visible range using

Fig. 4. The electronic spectra and their Gaussian analyses in dichloromethane.
 (A) $UO_2Cl_2 \cdot 2Ph_2SO$
 (B) $UO_2Br_2 \cdot 3Ph_2SO$

Fig. 5. The electronic spectra and their Gaussian analyses in dichloromethane.
 (A) $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2Ph_2SO$
 (B) $UO_2(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 5Ph_2SO$ } (Cell thickness 2 cm)

Fig. 6. The electronic spectrum and its Gaussian analysis of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2(PhO)_2PO$ in dichloromethane.

Fig. 7. The electronic spectra and their Gaussian analyses in acetonitrile.
 (A) $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_4$ (B) $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_4$.

glass cells. Such spectra in the U.V. region were obtained in Beckmann DB recording spectrophotometer using quartz cell.

References

1. A. K. MAJUMDAR and R. G. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29, 2359.
2. A. K. MAJUMDAR and R. G. BHATTACHARYYA, *Science and Culture* (Calcutta), 1969, 35, 271.
3. A. K. MAJUMDAR and R. G. BHATTACHARYYA, *Chem. and Ind.* (London), 1970, 95.
4. A. K. MAJUMDAR, R. G. BHATTACHARYYA and D. C. BERA, *Chem. and Ind.* (London), 1971, 730.
5. A. K. MAJUMDAR and R. G. BHATTACHARYYA, *Proc. Chem. Symp.*, 1970, 1, 293.
6. S. P. MCGLYNN and J. K. SMITH; *J. Mol. Spectroscopy*, 1961, 6, 164.
7. Z. DORI and H. B. GRAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 1395.
8. J. P. DAY and L. M. VENANZI, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1966, 1363.
9. A. K. MAJUMDAR and R. G. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* (In press).
10. G. J. JANZ and S. S. DANYLUK, *Chem. Rev.*, 1960, 60, 209 and references therein.
11. J. L. RYAN, 'Absorption spectra of Actinide compounds, M.T.P. Internat. Rev. Sci. Inorg. Chem. Ser. 1, Vol. 7, Ed., K. W. Bagnal, Butterworths, 1972.
12. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1955, 9, 405.
13. K. NAKAMOTO and P. J. MCCARTHY, "Spectroscopy and Structure of metal-chelate compounds", John Wiley, N.Y., 1968.
14. G. LEANDRI, A. MANGINI and R. PASSERINE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1386.
15. H. H. JAFFE and M. ORCHIN, "Theory and application of ultraviolet spectroscopy", John Wiley, N.Y., 1964.